

Hoping Well: AG-MRW-19-0545

[American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research <agri@scientificresearch.co>](mailto:agri@scientificresearch.co)

Mon 12/16/2019 6:32 PM

Junk E-Mail

To: 'Mattan Schlomi' <mattanschlomi@aol.com>;

Cc: 薛馬坦 <mshelomi@ntu.edu.tw>;

Importance: High

Dear Dr. Schlomi Mattan,

We worried over your wellbeing condition. Expect all is well at your end.

We wish to hear that there is no reason to worry.

If you are doing well please reply to this mail.

Anticipate your answer.

Regards,

Catherine Nichols!

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